

Syntheses of some 2-Aryl-3-benzoylchromones

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CHROMONES with benzenoid substituents at position-2 have been found to possess pharmacological activity¹. 2-Aryl-3-arylchromones are also known for their biological activity². The presence of methyl group and/or halogen atom often enhances biological activity³. Nitro group has also been found to be present in some of the biologically active compounds. Hence, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some new 2-aryl-3-arylchromones, the 2-aryl and 3-aryl moieties of which carry a nitro and *N,N*-dimethyl groups and the benzenoid ring of the chromone moiety invariably carries either a methyl or a halogen or both as substituents.

2-Hydroxyacetophenones (**1a-d**) were esterified with substituted benzoic acid in pyridine with phos-

phorus oxychloride. The esters (2a-d) were made to undergo a base-catalysed internal Claisen condensation to yield the related 1,3-diketones (3a-d), which were then condensed with different substituted aromatic aldehydes in ethanol containing catalytic amount of piperidine to obtain 2'-hydroxy-2-aryl-3-arylacrylophenones (4a-e). The acrylophenones (4a-e) were then cyclised in the presence of hydrogen peroxide and alkali to yield the target flavones (5a-e). An alternative method was also used to synthesise the chromones (5a-e) in which the acrylophenones (4a-e) were refluxed in isoamyl alcohol with selenium dioxide.

All the chromones obtained from the above two routes had identical melting points and spectra. All the compounds analysed correctly for C and H. Ir spectra of the chromones revealed peaks at 1640-1625 (C=O), 1565-1555 (C=C) and 1340, 1325 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C). Pmr spectra of two representative compounds further established the structure.

Experimental

Melting points of all the compounds were recorded in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The ir spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Beckmann spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO-d₆) on a Varian instrument (90 MHz).

o-Benzoyloxyacetophenones (2a-d): To a solution of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (1a-d; 0.0065 mol) and substituted benzoic acid (0.007 mol) in dry pyridine (2.5 ml), POCl₃ (0.4 ml) was added with constant stirring at 80-90°. After 2 h the mixture was treated with ice-cold HCl (1:1) and the resulting solid was crystallised from a suitable solvent: 2a (80%), m.p. 89-90° (methanol); 2b (70%), 130-31°, (ethanol); 2c (70%) 83-84° (ethanol); 2d (60%), 120-21° (methanol).

o-Hydroxydibenzoylmethanes (3a-d): Benzoyloxyacetophenone (2a-d; 0.001 mol) dissolved in anhydrous pyridine (5 ml) was stirred with KOH (0.003 mol) at room temperature for 2 h with exclusion of moisture. The resulting viscous mass was decomposed with ice and dilute HCl and the product was recrystallised from a suitable solvent: 3a (84%), m.p. 185-86° (ethyl acetate); 3b (75%), 149-50° (ethanol); 3c (70%), 134-35° (ethanol); 3d (55%), 188-85° (ethyl acetate).

2'-Hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenones (4a-e): *o*-Hydroxydibenzoylmethane (0.005 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) was mixed with a substituted benzaldehyde (0.005 mol) in ethanol and piperidine (0.3 ml) and the mixture was stirred at 60°. On cooling the solid that separated was crystallised from a suitable solvent: 4a (56%), m.p. 196-97° (ethanol); 4b (70%), 142-43° (ethanol); 4c (80%), 140-41° (methanol); 4d (64%), 169-70° (ethyl acetate); 4e (70%), 209-10° (ethyl acetate).

- a; R₁=R₂=H, Z=Y=NO₂
 b; R₁=H, R₂=Cl, Z=Cl, Y=NO₂
 c; R₁=H, R₂=Cl, Z=Cl, Y=N(CH₃)₂
 d; R₁=H, R₂=CH₃, Z=Cl, Y=NO₂
 e; R₁=Br, R₂=CH₃, Z=OMe, Y=NO₂
 R=C₆H₄ in all cases except in (e) where R=C₆H₄, CH=CH

2-Aryl-3-benzoylchromones (5a-e). Method 1: To compound 4 (0.001 mol) dissolved in methanol (70 ml), NaOH solution (2N) was added dropwise with stirring and occasional cooling by the addition of H₂O₂ (18%; 9 ml). The mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and the resulting solid

was dried and crystallised from a suitable solvent : **5a** (50%), m.p. 249–50° (acetic acid) ; **5b** (55%), 308–9° (acetic acid) ; **5c** (60%), 230–31° (methanol) ; **5d** (60%), 266–37° (acetic acid), δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.7–8.68 (11H, m, ArH) ; **5e** (50%), 264–65° (acetic acid), δ (CDCl₃) 2.40 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.68 (3H, s, OCH₃), 8.0–8.6 (10H, m, ArH).

Method 2 : A mixture of isoamyl alcohol (25 ml), 2'-hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenone (0.001 mol) and selenium dioxide (3.3 g) was heated for 12 h in an oil-bath at 150–60°. The mixture was then cooled, filtered and subjected to steam distillation to remove isoamyl alcohol. The residue was extracted with benzene. The extract was washed with cold aqueous sodium carbonate and water, evaporated to dryness and the resulting solid was crystallised from a suitable solvent : **5a** (30%), **5b** (32%), **5c** (35%), **5d** (3%), **5e** (35%).

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References

1. H. KOIKE and FOLIA, *Pharmacol. Jpn.*, 1981, **12**, 89 ; T. FUKUNDA, *Arch. Expt. Pathol. Pharmacol.*, 1932, **164**, 585 ; J. J. WILLIAM, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc. Sci.*, 1955, **44**, 404.
2. W. B. GRIGER and J. E. CONN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 112 ; Z. ARIYAN and H. SUCHITZKY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2242.
3. K. A. THAKER, D. D. GOSWAMI and D. C. PACHOR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 420.